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Review Article

A Review Article on Cosmetics Usage and Its Relation to Gender, Age and Marital Status

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ABSTRACT

The use of makeup to improve appearance dates back to ancient times. Consider the ancient Egyptians, who applied cosmetics consisting of copper and lead ore. When it comes to their beauty requirements, ancient women were frequently creative. Among other things, berries were used to darken lips and eyelids, as well as the ashes of burned matches. Businesses, organizations, and institutions have been working to find the best recipe for attracting customers and achieving growth from all angles for centuries. Investigating the relationship between cosmetic use and specific demographic factors including age, gender, and marital status is the goal of the current study. The findings show that demographic factors like age, marital status, and gender. In comparison to single men, married guys use cosmetics more frequently. Notwithstanding their use, cosmetics have a negative side. Neurotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, carcinogenicity, and other health hazards are associated with many additive substances, such as trace heavy metals. Educating individuals about cosmetic chemicals and their harmful effects is essential. This study examines the current state of cosmetic use in India, consumer behavior, the motivations behind cosmetic use, and the amount spent on beauty products. There are ways that the general people may help reduce the impact of dangerous ingredients in cosmetics.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics were created at least 7,000 years ago in almost every society on the earth. There are those who argue that the earliest ritual in human history was cosmetic body painting. Evidence for this can be seen in crayons associated with the advent of Homo sapiens in Africa, which use red mineral

colors like red ochre. The usage of cosmetics dates back to ancient Egypt and Greece, and archeological evidence confirms this. The Romans' description of skin creams made of beeswax, olive oil, and rosewater, as well as the use of castor oil as a protective balm are mentioned as instances of early significant developments in

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ancient Egypt. Ancient Greece also made use of cosmetics. References to cosmetics in the Old Testament can be found in 2 Kings 9:30, where Jezebel, in 840 BC, painted her eyelids. The book of Esther also discusses some beautifying methods. Even though the majority of Roman literature implies that cosmetics were not appropriate, they were utilized in ancient Rome. It is well known that certain women in ancient Rome created cosmetics such as lead-based skin-whitening treatments and kohl for eye lining. It is commonly known that ancient Egypt used cosmetics. Kohl first showed up in North Africa. treatments for wrinkles that include fresh moringa and gum of frankincense. A specific ointment was prepared using sycamore juice, kohl, and red ochre to treat burns and scars. Alternatively, frankincense and/or carob grounds were used to make a poultice, which is still used today. It has been found that jars of what could be called setting lotion contain a mixture of beeswax and resin. These were also used to cure conditions including baldness and graying hair. By applying these items to their moms, they believed they would make them irresistible in the afterlife. One thing that ties us all together is that we are all consumers. The truth is that everyone on the earth is a consumer. But when it comes to buying, everyone has different tastes, behaviour patterns, and dislikes.

The first textbooks on consumer behavior were produced in the 1960s, making it a relatively recent topic, but its intellectual forebears go back much longer. For example, several prominent psychiatrists addressed conspicuous consumption in 1899. Ads from the early 1900s also emphasized the importance of psychological principles. In the 1950s, Freudian principles were popularized by motivation researchers and embraced by advertising. It became evident that consumer behavior research was required by the 1950s, when the marketing concept was developed. According to Theodore Levitt, a marketing idea reflects "the view that an industry is a customers satisfaction process not a goods-producing process." The demands of the consumer, not a patent, a raw material, or a sales plan, are what drive an industry. [1] In the same manner, you may have specific preferences for certain foods, clothing, books, magazines, hobbies, strategies to save money, and stores that you enjoy going to. Your husband may not be the only one with these tastes. Each consumer is unique, and this is reflected in their behaviors, purchase processes, and consumption habits. Research on consumer behavior explains the reasons behind the various purchases and product usages made by customers.

Fig 1: Cosmetic Products

An outline of the corpus of research on cosmetics-related consumer behavior is what this chapter's part aims to accomplish. These evaluations emphasize the significant research that has been

done both in India and outside. In addition, this examination examines advertising, consumer preferences, cosmetic markets, and consumption trends. This chapter reviews a large amount of

research on the attitudes, behavior, and perceptions of cosmetic consumers. Throughout the ages, people have utilized natural resources such as leaves, seeds, and extracts to improve their appearance and well-being. An enormous industry that is expanding daily was born out of this lifelong interest. The continually increasing use of cosmetics is accompanied by an expansion of the industry's market share. The goal of this chapter's section is to provide an overview of the body of research on consumer behavior connected to cosmetics. The important research conducted both inside and outside of India is highlighted in these assessments. Furthermore, this analysis looks at consumer trends, cosmetic marketplaces, advertising, and consumer preferences. A significant body of research on the attitudes, actions, and perceptions of cosmetic consumers is reviewed in this chapter. People have used natural resources like leaves, seeds, and extracts to enhance their appearance and general well-being for centuries. This lifetime fascination gave rise to a massive industry that is growing every day. The market share of the cosmetics sector is growing in tandem with the steadily rising use of cosmetics.[2]

Review Of Literature:

Reviews regarding consumer behaviour towards cosmetics:

1.Nancy Et Coff et al, 2004, stated that young women like deodorant, perfumes, and makeup to seem pleasant, youthful, and physically attractive in her article "The real truth about beauty: A global report". [3]

2.Brion Davies, 2006, He wrote in "Colors Emerging Strategy Promotes Trade Up" that Indian women still use natural, home-made products a lot, which keeps the makeup business going strong.[4]

3.Tarang Vaish, 2006, He noted that most Indian consumers were brand loyal and sought value for their money in his study, "Cosmetics buying

behavior in India." Thus, the market has been dominated by brands like Lakme, Revlon, and L'Oreal. Women in their middle age and young people between the ages of 18 and 24 currently favor herbal products over chemical-based cosmetics because they believe the former to be less dangerous. Users of cosmetics have better physical and psychological perspectives in addition to having a more positive self-image. Customers will appear more appealing and better-looking on the outside, and because they believe they are presentable and lovely in the eyes of others, this confidence will translate into their mental state. [5]

4.Urvashi Makkar et al, 2007, found that the middle class population, which has seen a significant increase in disposable money, was the key target market for cosmetic items in their study "Changing attitude of consumers from chemical to Herbal cosmetics in India." Herbal cosmetics are preferred by cosmetic customers across a range of income brackets. Women were currently exposed to a wide range of cosmetic items through window displays, magazines, newspapers, pamphlets, and television commercials. Through various media, customers of cosmetics were informed about the quality of the products, the unique advantages, and the savings available. [6]

5.Diana Dodson, 2008, The speedier and better application of makeup products was the main topic of her article, "Rapid innovation keeps the color cosmetic category from stagnating in the mature markets." The primary driving force behind the extensive improvement in mascara brushes in recent years has been women's preference for eye cosmetic products. The nail products industry is steady and thrives because to the creative introduction of better brushes that enable faster and more accurate application of nail polish. [7]

6. Virginia Graham et al, 2009, indicated in their article "India: Country overview" that all women aspire to look attractive with the application of

cosmetics. The growing number of professional women had very specific tastes when it came to selecting makeup colors that would help them blend in with society. The color cosmetics industry in India is one of the industries with the quickest growth rates as a result of these factors. Devoted customers were prepared to shell out any

amount for their preferred brand. The price increase has little effect on their purchasing habits. Simultaneously, buyers who prioritize affordability and disregard qualification tend to favor affordable cosmetics. [8]

Male cosmetic consumption behaviour:

Fig 2: Male Cosmetics Usage

7. Arora, S, Gupta , S, 2013, investigated the opinions of men who purchase skincare goods, with a particular emphasis on identifying the variables affecting men's purchasing decisions for these items. The study made an effort to determine whether certain demographic variables, such as age and occupation, had any discernible effects on these aspects. This study aimed to offer insights into customer purchasing behavior and preferences for male skincare products that could benefit marketers operating in the rapidly expanding metrosexual sector. Men's purchasing behavior for skincare products in relation to the extracted characteristics was found to be influenced by age and occupation in a mixed way. The research will yield valuable insights that will help marketers better access the market and design targeted marketing and communication strategies.[9]

8. Dr. Pooja desh mukh , 2015, stated that "The analysis clearly shows that there are more men than ever in the traditional female market." This study looked into the variables influencing the erasing of gender roles in society. As a result of the

investigation, it is evident that there is a considerable correlation between one's own perception of oneself and society expectations around cosmetic usage. This study will assist marketers in recognizing the impending male cosmetic consumption trend and developing tactics that take the future 25-year-old age group into account. Male consumers' acceptance of using male cosmetics has been increasing. The increase in the number of uses is a result of rising social standards about men's attractiveness. The results of this study further highlight the significance of perception in determining how men consume. Also, statistics have demonstrated a strong correlation between monthly consumer goods spending and income, with young men now preferring cosmetics. [10]

9. Dr. Amol Ranadive ,2019, said that "there have been numerous modifications in the philosophy as Indian society has gradually absorbed western civilization. Cosmetics that were traditionally considered exclusively feminine or girlie are no longer seen as stereotypically taboo in Indian society. This has changed, as seen by the Indian

market. Since the previous ten years, a large number of businesses focused on male grooming have entered India and are doing fairly well. Despite the fact that respondents under 25 have a positive attitude toward cosmetics, he came to the conclusion that if advertisers effectively swayed them, they might begin using the products.

Marketers must begin promoting their products in novel and captivating ways since research indicates that consumers are not well-versed in the majority of cosmetic brands and products that are on the market. [11]

Female cosmetic consumption behaviour:

Fig 3: Female Cosmetics Usage

10. Anindita Audhkhasi, Pavni Arora, 2020, the Indian cosmetics sector is expected to grow by 25% to \$20 billion by 2025 as a result of increased consumer knowledge of beauty goods, rising personal grooming premiums, shifting consumption patterns, and rising purchasing power of women (Economics Times, 2019). In this work, the writers make an effort to examine and comprehend the ways in which psychological, societal, and economic elements have impacted women's cosmetic product purchasing decisions and contributed to this advancement. This study adopts an intersectional approach to examine how heteronormative beauty standards have contributed to the establishment of a culture that values "femininity," and how this has affected women's psychology and cosmetic purchasing habits. Their study aims to analyze the inclusion of the cosmetic sector while also analyzing how women's cosmetic purchase behaviors vary depending on the intersection of color, caste, race, religion, and other social variables. The study offers proof of how the cosmetics industry takes advantage of women's fears and helps to socialize

the inequity between genders. Pricing of cosmetics according to gender provides evidence of a direct link between the cosmetic industry's profit margin and its capacity to manipulate women. This study explores the ways in which patriarchal norms and beauty standards have forced women to spend more for cosmetics than men do, therefore contributing to their own economic oppression. Thus, the authors hope to gain an understanding of women's cosmetic shopping behavior patterns, the part inter sectionality plays in these patterns, and the extra money women are willing to pay to be considered attractive. She came to the conclusion that Indian consumers are mostly motivated to buy cosmetics based on pricing rather than considering the product's raw materials, chemical compatibility, or environmental friendliness. After overcoming financial constraints, women report feeling afraid of being made fun of for prioritizing their looks and spending money on makeup because they grew up in a setting where fundamental survival necessities aren't assured. When it comes to digital engagement rates in the personal care items

department, consumers from Tier I and Tier II cities are comparable to those from metro areas. Price comparisons, however, differ greatly. Due to a lack of awareness of new products and the presence of regional businesses with higher price margins, consumers in rural areas tend to stick with their established brands. A study carried out in Bangalore, India concluded that ads have no discernible impact on the purchasing behavior of Christians, Muslims, or Hindus. [12]

11. Dr. K. Mahalakshmi, 2023, said that women have been using cosmetics to increase their appearance since the beginning of human history. These days, cosmetics are more important in daily life. Indian women are joining the corporate sector and achieving financial independence. In general, women place a high value on fashion and cosmetics. At different stages of their lives, women started applying makeup. Women view makeup as a sorcery that enhances their beauty and self-confidence while they are young or adolescent. When it comes to choosing a product, female buyers have a lot of options based on factors like quantity, quality, price, and design. The study of consumer behavior focuses on how consumers choose what to buy, need, and want. Consumer purchasing is driven by the demands of the individual, the group, and the organization. Therefore, it is necessary to possess

a thorough awareness of how customers' purchasing behavior relates to the needs. Understanding how consumers interact with the marketing mix is crucial for comprehending their purchasing patterns. This is because each person has a different psychological response to goods and services depending on their culture, attitude, prior experiences, and perception. Based on these factors, the consumer must decide whether to make a purchase or not as well as where to get the preferred product. Consumers walk or go through a sequence of actions prior to purchasing a goods .They emphasize that the product should meet their demands, be of high quality, be reasonably priced, and provide them with features that add value. There are differences in consumer purchasing patterns with regard to product quality, price, status, features, and packaging. They largely follow the pulse of fashion, and their shifting tastes have an impact on their purchasing habits. Marketers invest millions of rupees in market research each year to uncover and forecast this shifting behavior. Because of the variety, low cost, and shifting trends in the cosmetics sector, marketers are currently having trouble understanding and targeting the behavior of their target audience. [13]

Cosmetic consumption behaviour of different age groups:

Fig 4: Cosmetics used by different age groups

12. Nilesh balvant anute, Anand deshmukh, 2015, they stated that :The majority of consumers who buy cosmetics are between the ages of 15 and 30. Domestic brands are preferred by the majority of consumers (65%). Sixty percent of consumers

choose to purchase organic cosmetics. Television is how nearly 50% of consumers learn about cosmetic products. 42.5% of the population uses cosmetics for beauty. Most people buy cosmetics from shopping malls and spend between Rs. 1000

and Rs. 2000 a month on them. The majority of consumers don't switch brands of cosmetics; they stick with what they use. [14]

13. Dr . Alpana Vaidya, Ameya patil , Kalpita tavkar , Vaishnavi raiturkar ,2023, they claimed that there has been a rise in the demand for cosmetics recently, particularly among young people worldwide. The goal of the current study was to comprehend youth consumption patterns for cosmetics. 181 individuals, aged 18 to 25, made up the study's sample (160 females and 21 males). Based on the questionnaire the researchers created, the data was gathered online using a Google form. In order to gain a deeper knowledge of purchasing decisions, interviews with nine consenting participants were also undertaken.. The study's findings demonstrated that the majority of respondents preferred skin care products over makeup, and over half of them had a daily face care regimen. It was observed that the participants bought one to three products each month and had varying monthly budgets. The great majority of respondents favored natural, simple makeup looks and preferred to buy cosmetics online. Friends, digital ads, and influencers were the primary sources of information about new products. Additionally, participants expressed a propensity to buy skincare-related products. [15]

Cosmetic consumption behaviour according to marital status:

14. Ojezele, Matlar ,2018, they made it clear that the usage rates by gender were 15.3% for men and 84.7% for women. The age group of 21–25 years old was found to use cosmetics the most (30.7%). Compared to married women (40.6%), unmarried women (58.9%) used cosmetics more frequently. 5.9% used it for bleaching, however 21.3% experienced different negative effects from using makeup. [16]

15. Rudrabhatla Prasanna ,2021, said that, Therefore, a study is conducted in the Hyderabad district of Telangana state to look at the differences

in the purchasing habits of married and single women with regard to beauty products. According to the survey, married women learn about cosmetics via friends, but the majority of single women learn about them from beauticians, cosmetic shops, etc. Most single women purchase makeup from high-end cosmetic shops, while married women get it from department stores. Married women do not wait for promotional offers, whereas single women like to purchase cosmetics during these times. Married women prefer a specific store because of the consistent quality and pricing of cosmetics, while single individuals do so because a variety of cosmetics are available. When it comes to choosing which cosmetics to buy, married women value their family's opinions more than single women do. Similarly, when purchasing cosmetics, married and single women place almost similar value on product quality, pricing, quantity, and ingredients. [17]

Reviews regarding adverse effects of cosmetics:

16. Kamala kant parashar , Namrata arya , 2018, said that new contaminants include chemicals found in cosmetics. They are only getting started with environmental monitoring. They do, however, pose health concerns to humans and freshwater and marine ecosystems because to their recognized various routes of environmental entry, which frequently involve water. Consequently, the term "cosmetovigilance" in public health research came to refer to a type of health surveillance where the goal is the safety of cosmetic products used for commercial purposes. We may feel more at ease with the items that are put on the market because of this surveillance, which is crucial for controlling potentially dangerous components. The use of preservatives, surfactants, fragrances, stains, and other substances in the production of cosmetic products has expanded in the cosmetics business in recent years. These compounds enhance the qualities,

characteristics, and durability of cosmetics, yet many of them are toxic to people and can cause anything from mild hypersensitivity reactions to anaphylactic shock or even death. Consequently, the careless use of makeup could pose a threat to public health. Future research in this area has greater potential because there are many cosmetics goods that are unexplored from this angle.

They concluded that, Dangerous compounds that are frequently present in cosmetic formulations have been related to recurrent negative effects and may be harmful to health. The regulatory and quality control frameworks for cosmetics vary

greatly throughout the world, but even so, they ought to be stricter when it comes to prohibiting the use of new, dangerous substances in cosmetic formulations in order to protect public health.

Applying a consistent cosmetovigilance globally is crucial to promoting advancements in the production, promotion, and public use of cosmetic products . This public health approach is a legitimate way of getting information on the safety of cosmetic goods and their components, avoiding the dangers connected with cosmetic use from becoming a major public health issue. [18]

Fig 5: Adverse effects caused by different chemicals present in cosmetics

17. Ruchi kohli , Anu mittal , Amit mittal , 2023, they came to the conclusion that, although cosmetics used to improve beauty are highly sought after, particularly by women, they also have a negative side. Cosmetics contain a number of hazardous additive chemicals that can cause a variety of health risks, including neurotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, carcinogenicity, endocrine disruption, reproductive disorders, and more. Examples of these chemicals include parabens, phthalates, polyethylene glycol, hydroquinone, resorcinol, 1,4 dioxane, and trace heavy metals. That's why the security of makeup is a major concern. It is imperative that individuals become conscious of the harmful impacts of cosmetic chemicals. This study examines the current state of cosmetic use in India, including the reasons behind women's purchases of cosmetics, their age group of choice, and their spending patterns on beauty goods. The detrimental impacts of cosmetics'

hazardous chemical compounds on he.alth are examined. The purpose of the study is to educate women about the numerous harmful substances included in cosmetics and how they might harm their health. It will also prompt scientists and medical professionals to look into the possible reasons for their unfavorable effects. [19]

Reviews regarding treatment of diseases caused by cosmetics:

18 . R. Dhankar , A. Hooda , 2011, they claim that biosorbents are employed in cosmetics to address the issue of heavy metal pollution. Compared to chemical resins, which use chemical resins as the main chemical adsorbent, biological adsorbents are less costly and more environmentally friendly. There are two categories for biosorbents. Corn husks and cobs are examples of agricultural byproducts and plants that provide the primary source. Microorganisms are the second and most prevalent type of biosorbent.

Plants cannot adsorb metals to the same extent as microorganisms can. In plant biology, sorbents utilise the spaces between tissues to adsorb metal ions, while microorganisms utilise the components of their cell walls and their metal-binding functional groups. In order to achieve heavy metal adsorption via processes like diffusion, surface adsorption, ion exchange, and complexation, microbial biosorbents rely on tube energy groups like carboxyl groups, phosphate groups, amine groups, and hydroxyl groups. The presence of functional groups significantly increases the ability of microbial biosorbents to adsorb heavy metals. [20]

19. Y.Lin , S. Yang , H. Hanifah , Q. Iqbal ,2018, Customers in general should be included as well. First, in order to protect the environment and maintain our safety, we should not buy cosmetics that have high concentrations of dangerous ingredients. Natural cosmetics, sometimes referred to as "green cosmetics," are composed of plant or fruit extracts and concentrations. In addition to requiring less water, energy, and raw materials than conventional cosmetics, green cosmetics are made without the use of chemicals or other artificial mixtures, which reduces environmental contamination. Reasonable trash disposal makeup is the second. For instance, when we go to the beach, we frequently see people discarding their used sunscreen bottles, which contributes to pollution. Cosmetics containers may also contain leftover cosmetics. If you throw them away carelessly, it can easily contaminate water or soil. Instead, dispose of cosmetics in the trash can, and the reusable plastic or paper box will be recycled by the garbage disposal station, which is a more environmentally friendly alternative. [21]

20. C.C.V. Franca, H.M. Ueno, 2020, says that, among other things, cosmetics producers should abide by national laws and regulations, take consumer and applicable government oversight seriously, and encourage customers to make

appropriate and environmentally responsible decisions. Making eco-friendly cosmetics is the cosmetics industry's primary responsibility. Ensuring that the product follows green chemistry principles is crucial when producing green cosmetics. Green chemistry is the complete process of designing, producing, and applying chemicals. By following the principles of green chemistry, the environmental impact of cosmetics can be reduced and potentially harmful compounds can be eliminated. demonstrated the need for involvement from the broader public as well, as clients. To preserve both our safety and the environment, the first step is to decline to buy cosmetics that have high concentrations of dangerous ingredients. Concentrations and extracts of fruits or plants are used to make natural cosmetics, commonly referred to as green cosmetics. Compared to conventional cosmetics, green cosmetics take less energy, water, and raw materials during production and don't include any chemicals or other non-natural mixtures, which helps to reduce environmental pollution. Second, affordable cosmetics for waste disposals. Take the pollution that results from people discarding their used sunscreen bottles when they go to the beach. Containers for cosmetics could contain leftover makeup. It is easy to contaminate soil or water if they are thrown out carelessly. Opt to dispose of cosmetics in the trash can; this is a more environmentally friendly option because the garbage disposal station will recycle the reusable plastic or paper packaging. [22]

CONCLUSION:

Consumer behaviour and variables like age, gender, and marital status are highly correlated. Women make up the majority of those who enjoy and use cosmetics, and their use tends to decline after marriage. When compared to single males, married guys typically exhibit more cosmetic traits. For the purpose of improving their appearance and gaining more social acceptance,

both sexes use cosmetics. Individuals in the 19–23 age range typically like and use cosmetics more. Because cosmetics are so widely utilized in daily life, it is common to ignore the harmful effects that their ingredients have on the environment as a whole. Many chemicals, such as parabens, phthalate, hydroquinones, pegs, and trace heavy metals, are present in cosmetics and personal care products, which are used by millions of men and women worldwide to improve their look. Therefore, it is crucial to research how they affect cosmetic safety, as this is a major concern. This article was written with the intention of increasing public awareness and providing concrete solutions to get rid of them in cosmetics.

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